

A Study on Customers Awareness on E-Commerce through Social Media

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Abstract

In this era, social media has become a vital part in our everyday life. E-commerce through social media includes activities like posting text and image updates, videos, and other content that drives audience engagement. Having said that, it is also a powerful tool for all businesses to reach prospects and customers by interacting through various mediums like WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram and so on. E-commerce through social media can help with several goals, such as increasing website traffic, building conversions, raising brand awareness, creating a brand identity and positive brand association, improving communication and interaction with key audiences. Our analysis aims at finding out the awareness level among customers regarding social media marketing that specifically includes WhatsApp, Facebook and Instagram only and the advantages and disadvantages to customers who buys products through social media.

Keywords: E-commerce through social media, customer awareness, advantages and disadvantages to customers.

Introduction Social Media

Social media refers to the websites and applications that enables the users to connect to people and facilitates easy and instant sharing of messages, pictures, videos and more. It has become an integral part in our daily lives. Social media not only serves the purpose of entertainment but in recent days it also plays a significant role in the commercial and business platform. Social media marketing is the fastest growing marketing trend with a reported 9 out of 10 businesses employing some form of a marketing campaign on social media. Retailers and small business owners make use of various social media such as WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram etc. to market their products, to attract more customers and thereby promoting sales. Through this, the cost involved in advertising and marketing the products on the part of the sellers is reduced. Not only it reduces the selling expenditure, but also it saves the time and provides the advantage of reaching a wide range of customers. Also, the feedback provided by the consumers enables businesses to identify the taste and preferences of the customers and there by implanting necessary changes in their goods or services.

Facebook

Facebook pages are far more detailed than Twitter accounts. They allow a product to provide videos, photos, longer descriptions, and testimonials where followers can comment on the product pages for others to see.

WhatsApp

It is used to send personalized promotional messages to individual customers. WhatsApp is also used to send a series of bulk messages to their targeted customers using broadcast option. Companies started using this to a large extent because it is a cost-effective promotional option and quick to spread a message.

Instagram

Instagram has proven itself a powerful platform for marketers to reach their customers and prospects through sharing pictures and brief messages. For companies, Instagram can be used as a tool to connect and communicate with current and potential customers.

Customer Awareness

Consumer awareness, which refers to a buyer's knowledge of a product or company, allows the buyer to get the most from their purchases. Consumers can make well-informed choices about what to buy and how much to spend when they have product information. The understanding by an individual of their rights as a consumer concerning available products and services being marketed and sold. The concept involves four categories including safety, choice, information, and the right to be heard.

Objectives

- To study about the awareness about e-commerce through social media.
- To identify the advantages of e-commerce through social media.
- To know the customers preferences about different categories of product.
- To study the customer awareness about the features of social media marketing.

Need and Importance of the Study

The study was significantly used to determine that buying product through social media was better than other online shopping. The need of study was to know the most preferred social media for trade and the reason for the preference. Rating of the trade was made based on the features of social media.

Scope of the Study

Customers awareness on e-commerce through social media in Chennai were contacted for study. The study could be extended to other parts of India. Social media like WhatsApp, Facebook and Instagram was focused but study can be absorbed through other social media also.

Research Methodology

Data collection

The data had been collected from primary source through questionnaire and also from secondary sources that is, from published articles, magazines and books.

Sample size

Responses were collected from 70 respondents from different occupations in Chennai city.

Research design

Descriptive research design was employed. The collected data were analyzed using statistical techniques to arrive at findings and conclusions.

Sampling technique

Stratified random sampling technique was employed to choose the sample based on the predefined framework that define the population under study.

Statistical Tools Used

The following statistical tools were used for the study:

- a) Percentage Analysis
- b) Weighted Average
- c) Garrett's ranking Technique

Limitations

1. Study was focused only on respondents in Chennai city
2. Sample size is limited that the findings cannot be generalized to all.

Review of Literature

1. **Anukrati Sharma (2012)** in her research titled "A Study on E-Commerce and Online Shopping: Issue and Influences" determined the changes in buying patterns and analysed the growth of e-commerce. Data had been collected by the questionnaire and interviews had been taken of 250 respondents. Tabulation, percentage analysis was the tools used. The research found out that most of the time customers preferred to shop clothing and accessories from online shopping websites.. It had been concluded that online shopping and e-Commerce were an important part of B2B in the present world.
2. **C. Arul Jothi and A. Mohmadraj Gaffoor (2017)** in their research titled "Impact of Social Media in Online Shopping" had determined the post purchase behavior of consumers. Data was collected from 70 respondents through questionnaires. The analysis was made through Percentage Analysis, Cross Tabulation, Chi Square Test and Mean Score. They had found that male was purchasing higher number of products through online than female. The interference of this research was that people use the combination of various sources for making final purchase decision.
3. **Neha Gupta and Dr. Deepali Bhatnagar (2017)** in their research titled "A Study on Online Shopping Behavior Among the Students" identified the behavior of the students and factors influencing while they buy the product. The data was collected from 100 respondents by questionnaire given to students while the secondary data was collected through published sources like magazines, journals, etc. and has been analysed through simple random sampling. They found that price played an important role and clothing was the highest buying product in online. It was concluded that online had truly revolutionized and influenced our society as a whole and the internet is often referred to as a borderless market.
4. **Jaimin Kamleshbhai Patel (2018)** in his research titled "Study of Consumer Perception on Online Shopping" analyzed the factors affecting consumer perception towards online shopping. A sample size of 100 consumers had been taken and primary data had been collected through structured questionnaire. The research had been analyzed with the help of factor analysis. It revealed that mostly the youngsters are attached to the online shopping. The study concluded that the customer found it was very flexible and in case of online shopping it delivered products quickly.

Analysis and Interpretation

1. Gender

Gender	No. of Respondents (In %)
Female	69
Male	31
Total	100

Inference

Table and chart unfolded that 31% of the respondents are male and 69% of the respondents are female.

2. Occupation

Occupation	No. of Respondants	Percent
Student	38	54.29
Self employed	9	12.86
Professional	14	20.00
Others	9	12.86
Total	70	100.00

Inference

The table and diagram showed that 38% of the respondents belong to the student category, 9% of the respondents are self-employed, 14% comprises of professionals, and 9% of the respondents belong to other kinds of occupation.

3. Income

Income	No. of Respondants
0-15000	39
15000-30000	10
Above 30000	21
Total	70

Inference

Table and chart unfolded 39% of the respondents are in the 0-15000 income category, 10% of the respondents are 15000-30000 income earning group, and 21% of the respondents are above 30000 income holders.

4. Account Holder

Account Holder	No. of Respondents	Percent
Yes	69	98.57
No	1	1.43
Total	70	100

Inference

Table and bar chart exposed that 98.57% are account holders and 1.43% of the respondents are non-account holders.

5. Most Preferred Social Media

Account Preferred	No. of Respondents	Rank
Whatsapp	37	1
Facebook	23	2
Instagram	9	3
Others	1	4

Inference

Table and pie chart represented that 37 respondents prefer WhatsApp, 23 prefer Facebook and remaining are Instagram and others.

6. Reason For Preferred Social Media

Reason	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Easily Accessible	25	35.71
Convenient	27	38.57
Safety	14	20.00
Others	4	5.71
Total	70	100

Inference

Table and pie chart represented 35.71% of the respondents find it easily accessible, 38.57% find it convenient, 20% find it safer and rest 5.71% opt for other facilities.

7. Preferred Product

Name of the Product	No of Respondents	Percent
Clothes	21	30
Gadgets	26	37
Jewelry	8	12
Others	15	21
Total	70	100

Inference

Table and chart showed that 30% of the respondents prefer buying clothes, 37% prefer gadgets, 12% go for jewellery, and 21% prefer other range of products.

8. Factor Affecting Trade Through Social Media

Factor	Total	Weighted Average	Rank
Time On Delivery	422	28.13	1
Saves Time	291	19.40	2
Direct Contact Between Buyer And Seller	288	19.20	3
Budget Friendly	269	17.93	4
Less Risky	245	16.33	5

Inference

Weighted average unfolded that time on delivery was the most influential factor while other factors like time saving, direct contact, budget friendly plays a vital role. Risk less was considered as latest factor.

9. Garrett Ranking For Features of E-Commerce Through Social Media

Factors	1St*79	2nd*66	3rd*57	4th*50	5th*43	Total	Average	Rank
Social Media Automation Using Api Provide Latest Updates And Regular Promotional Messages	316	330	912	1700	645	3903	55.78	1
Search By Location is a Highly Convenient Feature	316	264	570	1800	860	3810	54.43	2
Voice Note Facilitate Clarity in Effective Communication	0	330	1311	1400	731	3772	53.89	3
Api Integration Facilitates the Users to Track the Product Delivery Status	0	462	684	1700	860	3706	52.94	4
Wider Range of Products are Available for Easy Shopping	237	264	399	1050	1634	3584	51.20	5

Inference

Henry Garrette’s technique was used to rank the preference indicated by respondents on different factors. The ranking revealed that respondents rank promotional update by API as the most significant criterion. Search by location was ranked second followed by voice note facilities, API integration and wide range of product.

Suggestions and Conclusion

Suggestions

1. Measures must be taken in order to spread awareness among consumers in the form of advertisements and other modes of marketing.
2. Variety of offers and discounts may also pull in customers attention.
3. Communication plays a very important role in creating awareness.
4. Increase in the number of users of social media will increase the social media business.
5. Easily accessible is the most influential factor for trading through social media.

6. Social media automation using API provide latest updates and regular promotional messages are most preferred factor by the respondents in this study. Therefore, traders most concentrated on regular promotional updates.

Conclusion

This study aims at bringing out the level of awareness among a particulars size of population and it clearly concluded that most of the respondents are aware of what is happening in the social media business world and they prefer purchasing through social media because of the convenience that it provides, less purchasing cost and other facilities that makes their shopping ease. Therefore, it is no doubt that social media marketing is also growing rapidly like Amazon, Flipkart etc. and there will be better prospects for the social media entrepreneurs.

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